

Trends in Spectral Parameters and Nephelauxetic Ratio Values for some Lanthanoid(III)-Acetylacetonate Complexes

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It has been reported that the intensities of *f-f* electronic transitions are sensitive to changes in the immediate environment of lanthanoid(III) metal ions and the mode of metal-ligand interaction¹. Efforts have been made to utilise the oscillator strength values for specific electronic transitions of Ln(III) ions and their complexes for determining their stability constants² and thermodynamic parameters³. In continuation with our earlier studies on the electronic spectra of lanthanum(III) metal ions in different environments⁴, the present work was undertaken with a view to study the trends in the spectral parameters and nephelauxetic ratio values for Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III} and Er^{III} in complexation with acetylacetonate (acac).

Results and Discussion

The data in Table 1 show that the oscillator strength values (f_{JO}) attain a maximum at pH \approx 6.04, which is the pH of maximum complexation. A pH profile of the oscillator strength values (figure omitted for simplicity) exhibited a

TABLE 1—REPRESENTATIVE f_{JO} VALUES FOR [Ln^{III}-acac] COMPLEXES AT DIFFERENT pH VALUES

pH	f_{JO} ($\times 10^4$) for			
	¹ D ₂	³ P ₀	³ P ₁ ; ¹ I ₆	³ P ₂
	16 850	20 800	21 400–21 700	22 600
	<i>E</i> (cm ⁻¹)	<i>E</i> (cm ⁻¹)	<i>E</i> (cm ⁻¹)	<i>E</i> (cm ⁻¹)
2.00	2.815	1.192	2.622	8.065
(Std.)	(3.171)	(2.341)	(4.910)	(12.861)
5.03	2.305	1.241	2.818	6.474
5.71	2.566	1.845	2.869	6 134
6.04	2.882	1.777	2.998	6.214
6.50	2.918	1.734	2.440	7.530
7.02	1.720	1.798	1.997	5.885
7.37	1.280	1.716	1.901	5.039

maximum at pH \approx 5.5–6.00. Deviations beyond pH 6.5–7.0 may be on account of formation of hydroxo complexes. Table 2 records the f_{JO} values for the [Pr^{III}/Nd^{III}/Sm^{III}/Er^{III}-acac] at pH \approx 6.04, i.e. the range of maximum complexation. Separate studies on determination of concentration of [Ln(III)-acac] species at different pH values using SCOGS-NR computer software⁵ show (Figure omitted for brevity) good agreement with the above observations. The [Ln(III)-acac] concentrations were determined using the log K_n^H values for acac, the pK_w for water and the appropriate

log K_{ML}^M and log $K_{ML(OH)}^M$ values for the corresponding binary [ML] and hydroxo-complexes [MLOH]. An increase in the degree of complexation may also be visualised by the variations in the ²P_{1/2} assignment for Nd^{III}. The ²P_{1/2} assignment sensitive to the M-L interaction and the Ln(III) donor atom bond distance⁶ show a decrease in the energy [viz. pH 2.04, *E* (cm⁻¹) 23 543; pH 5.03, *E* (cm⁻¹) 23 501; pH 5.71, *E* (cm⁻¹) 23 470; pH 6.04, *E* (cm⁻¹) 23 377; pH 6.50, *E* (cm⁻¹) 23 488; pH 7.02, *E* (cm⁻¹) 23 570 and pH 7.37, *E* (cm⁻¹) 23 641] with increased pH values indicating greater release of inter-electronic repulsion with increased degree of complexation.

TABLE 2—OSCILLATOR STRENGTH VALUES FOR SOME SPECIFIC PROMINENT ELECTRONIC TRANSITIONS OF f_{JO} VALUES ($\times 10^4$) [Ln(III)-acac] COMPLEXES AT pH \approx 6.04

Assignment	[Pr ^{III} -acac]							
	¹ D ₂	³ P ₀	³ P ₁ ; ¹ I ₆	³ P ₂				
<i>E</i> (cm ⁻¹)	16 850	20 800	21 400–21 700	22 600				
f_{JO}	2.882	1.777	2.998	6.214				
Assignment	[Nd ^{III} -acac]							
	⁴ F _{3/2}	⁴ F _{5/2} ; ² H _{9/2}	⁴ F _{7/2}	⁴ G _{5/2}	² K _{3/2}	⁴ D _{3/2}		
<i>E</i> (cm ⁻¹)	11 450	12 500; 12 600	13 500	17 300	19 000	28 300		
f_{JO}	6.058	4.658	5.130	7.131	3.144	3.229		
Assignment	[Sm ^{III} -acac]							
	⁴ I _{13/2}	⁶ P _{3/2}	⁴ L _{13/2}	⁶ P _{7/2}	⁴ D _{3/2}			
<i>E</i> (cm ⁻¹)	21 600	24 000	24 550	26 750	27 700			
f_{JO}	6 178	6.896	6 016	1 351	1 662			
Assign- ment	[Er ^{III} -acac]							
	⁴ F _{9/2}	⁴ S _{3/2}	² H _{11/2}	⁴ F _{7/2}	⁴ F _{5/2}	² G _{9/2}	⁴ G _{11/2}	⁴ G _{9/2}
<i>E</i> (cm ⁻¹)	15 300	18 400	19 200	20 500	22 200	24 600	26 400	27 400
f_{JO}	8.499	3.015	4.359	1.063	4.996	5.207	1.408	2.487

The oscillator strength values (f_{JO}) composed of τ_λ parameters representing Ln(III)-L interactions (τ_2) and the symmetry around Ln(III) metal ion (τ_4 , τ_6) are recorded in Table 3. The parameters exhibit a general sequence $\tau_2 < \tau_4 < \tau_6$, based on their responses towards the Ln(III)-L interactions. The τ_λ parameters are also found to be higher for Pr^{III} and Nd^{III} than for Er^{III} which may be expected on account of higher symmetry produced with the former two due to their larger Ln(III) ion sizes. The τ_2 parameters are, however, smaller for Er^{III} than for identical Nd^{III} showing

a lesser involvement of covalency for post-Gd metal ions than for pre-Gd metal ions. These observations may be ascertained with the change in IERP-Racah (∂E^k) parameters and the nephelauxetic ratio ($\partial E^3/\partial E^1$) values (Table 3). Negative and smaller values of $\partial E^3/\partial E^1$ for Er^{III} than for Nd^{III} indicate a predominantly ionic pattern of bonding.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF τ_2 PARAMETERS ∂E^3 , ∂E^1 AND $\partial E^3/\partial E^1$ FOR [LN(III)-acac] COMPLEXES AT pH \approx 6.04

Parameters	Pr ^{III}	Nd ^{III}	Sm ^{III}	Er ^{III}
τ_2	-2.615	3.609	0.000	0.358
τ_4	2.811	1.592	7.451	3.862
τ_6	18.806	6.122	13.496	4.250
∂E^1	-35.24	72.86	-	-235.2
∂E^3	2.021	1.192	-	5.083
$\partial E^3/\partial E^1$	-0.0574	0.0163	-	-0.0216

The studies reveal that the oscillator strength values are susceptible towards the Ln(III) environment and their degree of complexation. The trends in τ_2 (smaller than τ_4 and τ_6) and $\partial E^3/\partial E^1$ (negative and smaller) values indicate that the Ln(III)-L interactions in the present case are predominantly ionic.

Experimental

Standard solutions of Ln(III) nitrates (99.99% purity, Indian Rare Earths Ltd.) and acac (Merck, G.R.) were prepared in double-distilled water. HNO₃ (0.1 mol dm⁻³) was used as reference acid. Carbonate-free NaOH solution (0.2 mol dm⁻³) was used to maintain the pH, which was recorded on an Orion-940 extended ion analyser system. Measured quantities of alkali were added to adjust the pH values; variations in concentration due to addition of alkali was calculated and used in the calculation for the oscillator strength values. The solutions of Ln(III) metal ions blank (0.025 mol dm⁻³) and [Ln(III)-acac] complexes (in 1 : 2 ratio) with total Ln(III) concentration of \approx 0.025 mol dm⁻³

were prepared and their electronic spectra recorded on a Perkin-Elmer Lambda 3B spectrophotometer.

The values of the oscillator strength and Judd-Ofelt parameter were evaluated using Judd-Ofelt^{7,8} approach. The variations in the inter-electronic repulsion Racah parameters (IERP-Racah) for Pr^{III}, Nd^{III} and Er^{III} were evaluated using Wong's equations⁹. Pascal compiled self-devised¹⁰ computer softwares were used to evaluate these spectral parameters using standard equations⁴.

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